

Our Partners

FAME is a joint effort of world-class experts in data management, data technologies, the data economy, and digital finance

Unique Features of the FAME Marketplace

FAME will provide a federated data marketplace that seamlessly integrates and trades diverse data assets across interconnected infrastructures.

FAME will offer a decentralized trading platform utilizing energy-efficient blockchain technology for transparent management of data asset lifecycles and monetization.

FAME will deliver trustworthy and energy-efficient analytics tools, enabling users to gain reliable insights while promoting sustainability.

Find out more about FAME:

 /FAME-Horizon

 www.fame-horizon.eu

Website

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 FAME-project

Newsletter

Objectives

Federated Marketplace & Open APIs: Develop a federated multi-cloud data marketplace platform with open APIs for secure data trading.

Interoperable Data Catalogue: Build a semantic, FAIR-compliant data catalogue for easier data discovery.

Energy-Efficient Analytics: Provide trustworthy, energy-efficient AI/ML analytics for data-driven insights.

Learning Center & Community: Build a vibrant community and offer training via a Learning Center with MOOCs.

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Secure Authentication & Compliance: Implement secure, compliant data access with authentication across federated data spaces.

Decentralized Data Trading: Enable decentralized data trading with blockchain tokenization, including NFTs.

Real-Life EmFi Pilots: Validate the platform with seven real-life Embedded Finance use cases.

FAME